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MS15 - Mapping of the stocktake of training materials across the training initiatives in the research communities of WP4 and a first assessment on gaps to be filled

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

1. Executive Summary

WP5 (Capacity building and recognition) of the EVERSE project collected a list of resources for capacity building as part of the work in task 5.1 (training resources). In cooperation with WP4 each science cluster and pilot was also asked about training resources relevant to their research software ecosystem. The list was then grouped by RSE topics and an online questionnaire among the project members conducted to evaluate the perceived value of those resources. This serves as a preparation to integrate the training resources into the RSQkit. It turns out that while the first steps in this direction are possible and will be taken, a broader feedback beyond the project partners is necessary to see statistically significant correlations within or between the science clusters. This will be done through an online workshop inviting all RSEs from the research clusters as well as institutional RSEs to contribute their learning paths and provide feedback on the so far curated resources from EVERSE.

2. Training material in the research clusters

The project partners collected know training materials in a collaborative fashion. Afterwards the material was grouped by RSE topics as well as domain specific resources, also to identify potential overlap. This is the list of accumulated resources:

1. Professional RSE Training Platforms/Resources

- [HIFIS RSE Training](#)
- [NL RS Training](#)
- [US-RSE Training Resources](#)
- [RSE Toolkit](#)
- [Training materials on different aspects of research software engineering \(including open source, reproducibility, research software testing, engineering, design, continuous integration, collaboration, version control, packaging, etc.\), compiled by the INTERSECT project](#)
- [Short online courses on various aspects of research software \(including FAIR\), by the NESC Research Software Support](#)
- [Intermediate Research Software Development](#)
- [eScience Center - Research Software Support](#)

2. Advanced RSE Curriculum Development

- [Alan Turing Institute - Research Software Engineering with Python](#)
- [Intersect Research Software Engineering Training](#)
- [Software Management Plans Guide](#)
- [SSI training hub](#)

3. High-Performance Computing, ML, Data Science Training/Schools/Programs

- [ASTERICS Programming School](#)
- [ESCAPE Data Science School](#)
- [UNIVERSE-HPC](#)
- [Gray Scott Battle School \(Heterogeneous Hardware Programming\)](#)
- [PUMPS+AI Summer School](#)
- [BSC Training Course: introduction to OpenACC](#)
- [BSC Training Course: introduction to CUDA Programming @ BSC](#)

4. Scientific/Parallel Computing Infrastructure & Training

- [CERN Schools on Computing](#)
- [HEP C++ Course and Hands-on Training](#)
- [NextGen Triggers Training](#)
- [HEP Software Foundation Training WG](#)
- [Basic Lab Skills for Research Computing](#)

5. Core FAIR/Open Science Practices, Principles & Methodologies

- [Tools and Practices for FAIR Research Software](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software](#)
- [Five Recommendations for FAIR Software by the Netherlands eScience Center and DANS](#)
- [The FAIR Cookbook, online recipes for life scientists that help make and keep data FAIR](#)
- [Good Enough Practices in Scientific Computing](#)
- [“Good Enough Practices in Scientific Computing” course](#)
- [Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. Sci Data 9, 622 \(2022\). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>](#)
- [Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 \(2016\). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.](#)

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- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#) - brief guides for different disciplines that can be used by the research community to understand how they can make their research (data and software) more FAIR
 - [10 easy things to make your research software FAIR](#), poster, part of Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things
 - [Open source definition](#), by the Open Source Initiative

6. FAIR Assessment and Quality Metrics

- [D5.2 - Metrics for Automated FAIR Software Assessment in a disciplinary context](#)
- [A self-assessment checklist for FAIR research software](#), by the Netherlands eScience Center and Australian Research Data Commons
- [EOSC Task Force for Code Quality Infrastructure](#)
- [EIROforum WG Training and Career Development](#)

7. Domain-Specific & Advanced FAIR Applications

- [FAIR for Machine Learning Interest Group](#)
- [CodeMeta terms](#)
- [The CodeMeta Project](#)
- [A cookiecutter software project template to kickstart a modern best-practice Python project with FAIR metadata](#)
- [Course: ResOps - Cloud-native Tools and Technology for Researchers](#)

8. Molecular and Computational Biology/Bioscience/Bioinformatics Training/Registries

- [TeSS Elixir](#)
- [ELIXIR-STEERS](#)
- [ELIXIR Data Platform](#)
- [ELIXIR Intrinsically Disordered Proteins Community](#)
- [Bioconductor Training Materials](#)
- [Git repositories with Bioinformatics training material](#)
- [Ed-DaSH](#)
- [Introduction to the Command Line for Metagenomics](#)
- [Introduction to R](#)
- [Tutorial: Workflows - Combining Tools for Data Analysis](#)
- [ENSEMBL REST API](#)

9. Ecological, Environmental & Biodiversity Research

- [ENVRI Knowledge Base](#)
- [LifeWatch ERIC Training Platform](#)
- [LifeWatch ERIC Summer Schools](#)
- [e-Biodiversity and Ecosystem Sciences Training Material](#)

10. Reproducibility Methodology/Frameworks

- ["Ten Reproducible Research Things" Tutorial](#)
- [Reproducibility for Everyone's \(R4E\) resources](#), community-led education initiative to increase adoption of open research practices at scale
- [CODECHECK](#), an approach for independent execution of computations underlying research articles
- [A Beginner's Guide to Conducting Reproducible Research](#), Jesse M. Alston, Jessica A. Rick, *Bulletin of The Ecological Society of America* 102 (2) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1002/bes2.1801>
- [The Turing Way's "Guide for Reproducible Research"](#), online book - part of the *The Turing Way: A handbook for reproducible, ethical and collaborative research*
- [Curated resources by the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training \(FORRT\)](#)

11. Research Transparency Tools

- [The Turing Way Community. \(2022\). The Turing Way: A handbook for reproducible, ethical and collaborative research. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233853](#)
- [Code Refinery](#)

12. Computational Skills Training/Foundational Carpentries

- [Software Carpentries](#)
- [Data Carpentry](#)
- [Posit \(Data Science resources - R, Python\)](#)
- [eScience Center Training](#)

13. Version Control and Collaboration

- [Software Carpentry Git Novice Lesson](#)
- ["How Git Works" Professional Course on Pluralsight](#)
- [VersionControl with Git](#)

14. Research Software Discovery and Management

- [Awesome Research Software Registries, a list of research software registries \(by country, organisation, domain and programming language\) where research software can be registered to help promote its discovery](#)

15. User Experience in Research Environments

- [Introduction to User Experience Design](#)

16. GPU/Parallel Programming Technologies - Scientific Acceleration

- [BSC Training Course: Introduction to CUDA Programming](#)
- [BSC Training Course: Introduction to OpenACC](#)
- [PUMPS+AI Summer School](#)
- [GPU Programming](#)
- [Parallel Programming in Python](#)
- [GPU Programming: When, Why and How?](#)
- [CUDA training](#)
- [OpenACC training](#)

17. Scientific/HPC Computing Languages - Scientific Acceleration

- [Introduction to Julia](#)
- [Julia for high-performance scientific computing](#)
- [Julia for high-performance data analytics](#)
- [Programming with Julia](#)
- [Foundation HPC Skills Course](#)

18. Build Systems & Compilation

- [Automation and Make](#)
- [CMake hands-on workshop](#)

19. Version Control, Collaborative Development & CI/CD

- [Version Control with Git](#)
- [Collaborative distributed version control](#)
- [Introduction to version control](#)
- [Continuous Integration / Continuous Development \(CI/CD\)](#)
- [Python Testing and Continuous Integration](#)
- [Workflows with Python and Git](#)

20. Cloud, DevOps & Workflow Automation

- [Tutorial: Workflows - Combining Tools for Data Analysis](#)
- [Course: ResOps - Cloud-native Tools and Technology for Researchers](#)
- [Introduction to Cloud Computing for Genomics](#)
- [Introduction to Workflows with Common Workflow Language](#)
- [The Missing Semester of Your CS Education](#)

21. Core Python Programming

- [Programming with Python](#)
- [Plotting and Programming in Python](#)
- [Level Up your Python](#)
- [Python Intro for Libraries](#)
- [Building Better Scientific Software in Python](#)

22. R Programming Foundations

- [R for Reproducible Scientific Analysis](#)
- [Introduction to R](#)
- [Programming with R](#)
- [Getting Used to R, RStudio, and R Markdown](#)
- [A ModernDive into R and the Tidyverse](#)

23. Specialised Computing, Programming & Debugging

- [Programming with MATLAB](#)
- [Introduction to the Internet of Things](#)

24. Software Quality Testing & Validation frameworks

- [Automated Testing - Preventing Yourself and others from Breaking your Functioning Code](#)

25. Software Documentation Strategies

- [How to Document your Research Software](#)
- [Software Citation](#)
- [Software Licensing](#)
- [Guide for Communication](#)

26. Research data management & analysis - databases

- [SQL for Humanities](#)
- [SQL for Business](#)
- [Database and SQL](#)

27. Research Computing Environments

- [Jupyter Notebooks - A tool to write and share executable notebooks and data visualization](#)

28. Software Packaging Strategies & Reproducibility

- [Python Packaging](#)
- [Guide for Reproducible Research](#)
- [Welcome to Python Packages !](#)

29. Software/Project Management, Architecture, Design, Development Practices & Methodologies

- [Introduction to User Experience Design](#)
- [Intermediate Research Software Development](#)
- [Managing Academic Software Development](#)

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- [Guide for Project Design](#)
 - [Managing Research Software Projects](#)

30. Shell & Command Line tools

- [Introduction to the Command Line for Metagenomics](#)
- [The Unix Shell](#)

31. Container Technologies & Orchestration

- [Reproducible Computational Environments using Containers: Introduction to Singularity](#)
- [Reproducible Computational Environments Using Containers: Introduction to Docker](#)
- [Introduction to Docker and Podman](#)

3. First evaluation

All resources were converted into an online questionnaire to ask the project partners how familiar they are with the resource and whether they believe the resource to be valuable. For each resource listed above the responders had the choices:

-1 = Drop from list

0 = Not known in our cluster

1 = Known but not used in our cluster

2 = Partially used in our cluster

3 = Fully integrated in our cluster

The question form for gathering input from the project partners was split into the two parts based on the initial tables from the resource accumulation: Groups 1-15 and 16-31. The first block of groups received more feedback, although the overall number of responses was too low to derive anything beyond a first impression.

3.1 Basic Capacity Building (Groups 1-15, 8 responses)

Respondent Demographics:

- There's diversity in the science clusters represented: ENVRI, SSH, PaNOSC, and ESCAPE, plus some respondents marking "None"
- Notable presence of "None" cluster affiliations indicating broader community reach
- Roles vary from technical managers to researchers, SWEs, RSEs, technical manager, and engagement and training officer

1. Key Patterns:

- Strong awareness of some FAIR principles and RSE-related resources
- The Carpentries (Software, Data) show consistent recognition
- Many resources are marked as "0" (unknown/unused) across multiple respondents

3. Interesting Anomalies:

- One respondent provided feedback about English language resources and suggested a star rating system
 - It suggests that language might be a barrier.
- Another respondent marking as "N/A" rates all resources as "-1", ie, "Drop from list" but except HEP resources CERN school, software carpentries, and "FAIR for RS"(rating "3")

4. Science Cluster Influence:

- ESCAPE cluster members show notably higher familiarity with ML/HPC/Scientific & Parallel computing-related resources (ASTERICS, ESCAPE, CERN Schools, HEP training, FAIR for ML IG: high ratings>="2")
- ENVRI cluster shows particular interest in FAIR principles, ELIXIR, for some bio and environmental science resources
- SSH cluster shows emphasis on basic programming, code refinery, CodeMeta, FAIR principles, and documentation tools
- PaNOSC cluster shows particular high rating for RSE training(HIFIS), RSE toolkit, R, carpentries
- Institutional affiliations strongly influence resource selection

5. Role-Based Usage Patterns:

- RSEs demonstrate higher familiarity with technical resources and programming tools

- Engagement/Training officer shows stronger awareness of documentation, ESCAPE DS school, CodeMeta, and some FAIR-related resources
- SWEs, researchers show higher familiarity with RS materials, FAIR principles, CodeMeta
- Technical manager tends to focus more on project management, FAIR practices, Posit, and workflow-related resources
- Data might hint at a potential niche for hybrid/multidisciplinary training modules
- One respondent marking as “None” shows some familiarity with some RS resources, reproducibility, software management, FAIR principles & CodeMeta (most ratings around “1”), some awareness with Bio-based materials (rating mostly between “0” to “2”), carpentries, git

6. Resource Awareness Distribution:

- Core programming resources (Git, Python) have higher recognition across most groups (though in some cases receive “-1” and “0” ratings)
- Some familiarity with the bio-related resources, but sporadic
- Some familiarity (Known, but not used/partially used) with Turing-related materials, CodeCheck, Code Refinery
- Resources based on reproducibility show moderate recognition in some responses
- Specialised tools (like GPU programming or specific domain tools) show low awareness
- Documentation, practical applicability, and best practices resources show medium but consistent awareness
- Some awareness about open science practices, CodeMeta, FAIR quality metrics across different science clusters and roles
- User Experience Design show no recognition

7. Knowledge Gaps:

- Most respondents show limited awareness of cloud computing resources
- Machine learning, AI and HPC-related training resources, like data science schools receive less recognition, more role and domain-specific
- Domain-specific resources outside one's field are largely unknown

8. Rating Patterns:

- Most responses cluster around “0”, few “-1” (unknown/drop from list)
- Ratings of “3” (high usage) appear mainly for established, well-known resources
- Several “-1” ratings suggest that particular resource should be dropped from the list
- Word of caution: Since only 8 responses are present. Some anomalies (like uniform “-1” or “0” ratings for certain resources) might be amplified by the small sample size.

9. Implementation Barriers

- Complex setup requirements limit adoption
- Resource discovery challenges across clusters
- Language barriers (predominantly English resources)

10. Cross-Form Correlations:

- Respondents who completed both forms show consistent rating patterns
- Resource awareness correlates strongly with role responsibilities

Comments left by responders:

- What are the other training resources your cluster uses that aren't listed above?

- There will be lists (such as <https://www.clarin.eu/content/digital-humanities-course-registry>) covering a range of topics including some introductory material to software development, fair data management etc...
- I guess you focus on resources written in english. That should be said explicitly. Also, we have here a confusing mix of training resources (mostly), by also working groups, papers, companies...
- Do you have suggestions for any other resources that are missing from this list?
- Core topics for software quality are software design including software architecture and design patterns, and software metrics and testing
- What alternative resources would you recommend instead of any you suggested dropping?
- Each RSE has its own preferred online tutorial about this or this tool. Would be nice to have the possibility to include it easily. And I suggest a system of stars to let the learners rank the tutorials. Thanks for this survey. I discovered many unknown nuggets in it !

3.2 More specific resources (Groups 16-31, 4 responses)

1. Respondent Demographics:

- The science clusters that are represented here: SSH, PaNOSC, and ESCAPE, plus one respondent marking "None"
- Roles vary from researchers, RSEs, and SWEs

2. Key Patterns:

- Lower response rate (4 vs 8) suggests possible survey fatigue
- Strong focus on programming and development tools
- Notably higher ratings for most respondents:
 - Version control resources, CI/CD
 - Python programming resources
 - Unix/command line tools
 - Container technologies

3. Technology Focus:

- Strong emphasis on basic programming tools rather than advanced technologies
- Higher ratings for version control, CI/CD, CL tools, and Python compared to specialised tools
- Moderate awareness of container technologies but underrepresentation compared to their growing popularity - might suggest a training gap in emerging technologies
- GPU/CUDA/Parallel programming/Julia show moderate recognition(might be role/cluster specific - one "None", one from ESCAPE)(Rating: "Known but not used" or "Partially used")
- UED shows no recognition
- R programming, specialised computing, SQL show very low recognition
- Low awareness for software documentation techniques, packaging, software/project management for most respondents
- Jupyter shows moderate recognition

4. Learning Path Preferences:

- Resources for foundational skills receive higher ratings
- More advanced or specialised topics show lower awareness(might depend on role/domain/expertise)

- Preference for practical, interactive, hands-on resources over pure theoretical ones
5. Cross-Form Correlations:
 - Respondents who completed both forms show consistent rating patterns
 - Resource awareness correlates strongly with role responsibilities
 6. Interesting Anomalies:
 - One respondent specifically mentioned HIFIS resources, suggesting regional/institutional preferences
 - Some respondents show high expertise in narrow areas (rating >= "2") but less familiarity in broader technological domains
 7. Resource Type/Format Preferences:
 - Interactive tools (Jupyter Notebooks) receive higher ratings
 - Documentation-focused resources show high usage
 - Complex technical tools show lower usage but high importance among specialists
 - Self-contained learning materials preferred
 - Tools requiring significant setup or prerequisites show lower adoption
 - Video-based or workshop-style resources receive mixed responses
 8. Interdisciplinary Knowledge Transfer:
 - Limited cross-pollination of knowledge between clusters
 - Domain-specific resources rarely recognised outside their primary field
 - Common tools (Git, Python, CL tools, containers) serve as bridges between disciplines - minimal evidence of interdisciplinary resource usage beyond these common tools
 9. Rating Patterns:
 - Most responses cluster around "0" (unknown)
 - Ratings of "3" (high usage) appear mainly for established, well-known resources
 - Some "-1" ratings suggest that particular resource should be dropped from the list
 - Word of caution: Since only 4 responses are present. Some anomalies (like uniform "0" ratings for certain resources) might be amplified by the small sample size.
 10. Science Cluster Influence:
 - ESCAPE cluster member shows notably higher familiarity with ML/Parallel Programming/Scientific computing-related resources (GPU/CUDA Programming, Julia, HPC)
 - Awareness about Automation and Make, Cloud Computing, CWL, R, MATLAB, Testing, Python Packaging, SW documentation techniques, SQL, Jupyter, Reproducible Research Guide, Project Design Guide, RS development & projects, and container technologies for that one particular respondent marking 'None' (most ratings are: "Known but not used", "Partially used" with a few "Fully used")
 - SSH cluster shows emphasis on the "The Missing Semester of Your CS Education"
 - Institutional affiliations strongly influence resource selection
 11. Role-Based Usage Patterns:
 - RSE demonstrates higher familiarity with technical resources and programming tools
 - SWE rates most resources as "0"

Comments left by responders:

- What are the other training resources your cluster uses that aren't listed above?
- HIFIS provided RSE topics: <https://www.hifis.net/services/software/training.html>

4. Gap Analysis

A full gap analysis was not possible with the responses from just the project partners. WP5 has agreed to rerun the questionnaire in an online-workshop format with the larger EOSC science communities in Q2/2025 to receive broader feedback and also allow for an inclusive process for adding other training resources to the project.